

APPROACHES TO THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article covers issues such as the competence of the teacher-educator in the formation and development of information competence, its content, the structure of information competence and its content.

Keywords: teacher-educator, competence, information competence, knowledge acquisition, knowledge acquisition, information literacy.

The 21st century is the century of education, knowledge, information, information and communication technologies. Mass computerization, the introduction and development of innovations have led to advances in industrial production of information technology.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the organization of systematic work to increase the scientific potential and professional competence of teachers in preschool education. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Upbringing" dated December 17, 2019, sets priorities for regulating relations in the field of preschool education and upbringing. In this regard, today the urgent task is to increase the professional competence of teachers, to train highly qualified personnel.

Today in the labor market the professional requirements of teachers to them have increased the competitiveness of specialists. Among other things, the qualities of a modern educator, the professional use of information and communication: technology and modern technical means; developed communication environment; information retrieval, analysis and processing, acquisition of new knowledge, etc. covers. Therefore, information competence occupies a special place among a wide range of competencies.

The concept of information competence of the educator is defined as "a complex individual-psychological product based on the integration of professional and specific knowledge, skills and qualities of the subject of the information society, which allows to effectively solve pedagogical tasks in the context of informatization of society and education."

His research has shown that the concepts of "information competence" and "information competence" are sufficiently broadly and effectively defined at the current stage of development of pedagogy (Dvoretzky SI, Tarov VP, Muratova OB Zaytseva, AL Semyonov, N.Yu. Tairova, O. M. Tolstoy). [2,3,].

Kay Raseroka, president of IFLA (International Federation of Library Associations), defines the concept of "information competence" in terms that define its various aspects of literacy, such as computer literacy; digital literacy, information technology literacy, competent use of Internet resources; rational use of library resources; promotes concepts such as tools; multidisciplinary competence; verbal literacy. [1]

It is necessary to theoretically substantiate the general approaches to modeling, the principles of grouping the main components of its structure to create a structure of

information competence of the teacher, reflecting the modern requirements to the professional qualifications of the educator. Qualification requirements are usually brought in many ways to a "specialist model (direction)" that defines the purpose of training and, consequently, its content, methods, tools. According to the classical approach, these requirements are formed in the form of requirements for knowledge, skills, abilities and personal qualities of the specialist on the basis of qualification scales (taxonomy). This approach, despite its advantages, is more suitable for educational activities than for professional or educational-professional activities.

Competencies mean the ability to solve pedagogical tasks in this group (pedagogical diagnostic tasks, pedagogical design tasks, etc.) on the basis of ICT [4]. That is, we understand a set of interrelated qualities of an individual, a harmonious form of knowledge, skills and abilities in the activity, which allows them to achieve professional goals set at the present stage of educational development.

"Education" is the first level, where educators gain knowledge on the use of information technology and acquire basic ICT competencies. Upon completion of this level of training, they should gain an understanding of the potential benefits of using ICT, as well as the possibilities of planning investments in ICT in accordance with policies and priorities. At this level, they continuously master the use of technology to further their independent learning and skills development.

Teachers-educators who have mastered the competencies at the level of "education":

- Explain how their classroom work relates to institutional and / or government policies and contributes to their implementation.
- Analyze educational standards and identify opportunities for pedagogical use of ICT to ensure compliance with standards.
- Rational choice of ICT to support specific learning and teaching methods.
- have an understanding of the functions of equipment and standard office programs and be able to use them.
- Organize a classroom to support a variety of inclusive teaching methods using technology.
- Can use ICT for independent professional development.

The second level is "Knowledge Acquisition", in which educators will have ICT competencies that will enable them to create a conducive learning environment focused on developing students and teamwork skills in the future. This degree also provides an opportunity to apply policy guidelines, take into account the real situation, support relevant school resources, and develop plans in the field of information technology to forecast future needs. In addition, educators can continue their knowledge by joining the community with local and international partners.

Teachers-educators who have mastered the competencies at the level of "knowledge acquisition":

- Development, modification and application of pedagogical practice in accordance with institutional and / or national policies, international documents (for example, the UN Convention) and social priorities;
- Incorporate ICT into the curriculum, teaching process and assessment system of a particular subject, creating a favorable environment for students to successfully master the curriculum using ICT;

- Designing project-based learning activities using ICT to help develop, implement and monitor project plans and solve complex problems;
- Integrate a variety of digital tools and resources to create an integrated digital learning environment to develop high-level thinking and problem-solving skills;
- A flexible approach to the use of digital tools to simplify the learning process collaboratively, organize work with the student and interact with other participants in the learning process;
- Can use technology to interact with the professional community for professional development.

The third level is “Knowledge Creation,” in which educators acquire skills that help them model best practices and create a learning environment that helps trainees develop the new knowledge they need to develop more appropriate, good, and prosperous societies.

Educators who have mastered the competencies at the level of “knowledge creation”:

- Critical assessment of institutional and public policy in the field of education, proposing changes, working on their improvement and predicting the impact of such changes in the future;
- Identify the most effective combination of child-centered and collaborative learning for student development in a multidisciplinary curriculum;
- Contribute to the self-education of students in the process of student-oriented and collaborative learning, setting only the basic criteria for such education;
- Participate in building knowledge communities and use digital tools to support inclusive education;
- Play a leading role in the development of ICT strategy in the organization of preschool education;
- Preschools can constantly evolve, experiment, innovate and share best practices to find the most effective ways to use information technology in organizations.

“Learning”, “Assimilation of Knowledge” and “Creation of Knowledge” and how the six dimensions interact. (See Table 1) Each form at the intersection of certain levels and aspects of education corresponds to the ICT competence of the educator.

Table 1

“The structure of ICT competence for teachers”

Measurements	Learning	Assimilation of knowledge	Creating knowledge
The role of ICT in education	Understanding politics	Apply the policy	Policy innovations
Digital skills	Application	Integration	Transformation
Professional development of teachers	Digital Literacy	Network collaboration	As an educator innovator

Based on this, we defined information competence and information competence.

Information competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies, the experience of using them in solving certain social and professional tasks with the help of new information technologies, as well as the ability to improve professional knowledge and

experience in the field. Mobilization of knowledge, skills and behaviors net activity is understood.

Information competence is an integral quality personality, which is the reflection of the processes of selection, assimilation, processing, the ability to find optimal solutions in various areas of cognitive activity, which allows to develop, receive, predict and implement information in an optimal special type.

From the general didactic point of view, the following stages of formation are the information competence of specialists in the system of technical education: computer literacy, information literacy, information competence.

Computer literacy is the acquisition of a minimum set of knowledge and skills, working on a personal computer, understanding the basics and meaning of computer science, mastering information technology in society. Computer literacy is not sufficient for human activity in the information society.

Information literacy is the best way to deal with information signs, models, data, information and to present them to the interested consumer, to solve theoretical and practical problems; improvement mechanisms, technical environment for production, storage and transmission of information; system development, training, preparation of people for effective use of information resources, awareness of information and telecommunications knowledge. It is important that the application of this approach in modeling modern requirements for the level of pedagogical professionalism is associated with global trends in the development of vocational education and the change of its scientific paradigm.

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